

OBJECT OF LEXICOLOGY

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Annotation: The term «Lexicology» is of Greek origin from «lexis» - «word» and «logos» - «science». Lexicology is the part of linguistics which deals with the vocabulary and characteristic features of words and word-groups. The term «vocabulary» is used to denote the system of words and word-groups that the language possesses.

Key words: General lexicology, special lexicology, descriptive lexicology, historical or diachronic lexicology, comparative Lexicology, relationship, approaches, vocabulary, investigation

The term «word» denotes the main lexical unit of a language resulting from the association of a group of sounds with a meaning. This unit is used in grammatical functions. It is the smallest unit of a language which can stand alone as a complete utterance. The term «word-group» denotes a group of words which exists in the language as a ready-made unit, has the unity of meaning, the unity of syntactical function, For example, the word-group «as loose as a goose» means «clumsy» and is used in a sentence as a predicative. "He is as loose as a goose". Lexicology can study the development of the vocabulary, the origin of words and word-groups, their semantic relations and the development of their semantic structure, change of meaning. [1,2,3,4,5,6]

language universals.

Special Lexicology deals with the words of a definite language. Ex.: English Lexicology , Russian Lexicology , Uzbek Lexicology and so on.

Descriptive Lexicology studies the words at a synchronic aspect. It is concerned with the vocabulary of a language as they exist at the present time.

Historical or diachronic Lexicology deals with the development of the vocabulary and the changes it has undergone. For example, in descriptive Lexicology the words «to take», «to adopt» are considered as being English not differing from such native words as «child», «foot», «stone» etc. But in historical Lexicology they are treated as borrowed words.

Comparative Lexicology deals with the properties of the vocabulary of two or more languages. In comparative Lexicology the main characteristic features of the words of two or more languages are compared. For example, Russian—English Lexicology, English—French Lexicology and etc.

Lexicology is closely connected with other aspects of the language: Grammar, Phonetics, The History of the language and Stylistics.

Lexicology is connected with grammar because the word seldom occurs in isolation. Words alone do not form communication. It is only when words are connected and joined by the grammar rules of a language communication becomes possible. On the other hand grammatical form and function of the word affect its lexical meaning. For example. When the verb «go» in the continuous tenses is followed by «to» and an infinitive, it expresses a future action. For example, he is not going to read this book. Participle II of the verb «go» following the link verb «be» denotes the negative meaning. For example. The house is gone.

So the lexical meanings of the words are grammatically conditioned.

Lexicology is linked with phonetics because the order and the arrangement of phonemes are related to its meaning. For example, the words «tip» and «pit» consist of the same phonemes and it is the arrangement of phonemes alone which determines the meaning of the words. The arrangement of phonemes in the words «increase» and «increase» is the same. Only stress determines the difference in meaning. [1,2,3,4,5,6]

Lexicology is also closely linked with the History of the language. In examining the word information in terms of its historical development we establish its French origin and study the changes in its semantic and morphological structures. If we don't know the history of the language it will be very difficult to establish different changes in the meaning and form of the words which have undergone in the course of the historical development of the language.

There is also a close relationship between Lexicology and Stylistics. The words «to begin» and «to commence» mean one and the same meaning but they can never be used interchangeably because they have different stylistic references.

The relationship existing between words may be either syntagmatic or paradigmatic.

The syntagmatic relationship is found in the context. The context is the minimum stretch of speech which is necessary to bring out the meaning of a word. For example, take tea (чой ичмок — пить чай), take tram (трамвайда юрмок — ехатъ на трамвае).

The paradigmatic relationship is the relations between words within the vocabulary: polysemy, synonymy, antonymy of words etc.

name" as Juliet says? These and similar questions are answered by lexicological research.

For some people studying words may seem uninteresting. But if it is studied properly, it may well prove just as exciting and novel as unearthing the mysteries of Outer Space.

It is significant that many scholars have attempted to define the word as a linguistic phenomenon. Yet none of the definitions can be considered totally satisfactory in all aspects. It is equally surprising that, despite all the achievements of modern science, certain essential aspects of the nature of the word still escape us. Nor do we fully understand the phenomenon called "language", of which the word is a fundamental unit.

We do not know much about the origin of language and, consequently, of the origin of words. It is true that there are several hypotheses, some of them no less fantastic than the theory of the divine origin of language. We know nothing — or almost nothing — about the mechanism by which a speaker's mental process is converted into sound groups called "words", nor about the reverse process whereby a listener's brain converts the acoustic phenomena into concepts and ideas, thus establishing a two-way process of communication. We know very little about the nature of relations between the word and the referent (i. e. object, phenomenon, quality, action, etc. denoted by the word). If we assume that there is a direct relation between the word and the referent — which seems logical — it gives rise to another question: how should we explain the fact that the same referent is designated by quite different sound groups in different languages. We do know by now — though with vague uncertainty — that there is nothing accidental about the

vocabulary of the language; that each word is a small unit within a vast, efficient and perfectly balanced system. But we do not know why it possesses these qualities, nor do we know much about the processes by which it has acquired them.

The list of unknowns could be extended, but it is probably high time to look at the brighter side and register some of the things we do know about the nature of the word.

We do know that the word is a unit of speech which, as such, serves the purposes of human communication. Thus, the word can be defined as a unit of communication. Then, the word can be perceived as the total of the sounds which comprise it and the word, viewed structurally, possesses several characteristics.

The modern approach to word studies is based on distinguishing between the external and the internal structures of the word. By the vocabulary of a language is understood the total sum of its words. Another term for the same is the stock of words. [1,2,3,7,8,9]

The external structure of the word is its morphological structure. For example, in the word post-impressionists the following morphemes can be distinguished: the prefixes post-, im-, the root press, the noun-forming suffixes -ion, -ist, and the grammatical suffix of plurality -s. These morphemes constitute the external structure of the word post-impressionists. The external structure of words, and also typical word-formation patterns, are studied in the section on word-formation.

The internal structure of the word, or its meaning, is nowadays commonly referred to as the word's semantic structure. This is certainly the word's main aspect. Words can serve the purposes of human communication due to their meanings, and it is most unfortunate when this fact is ignored by some

имконият (условия) «**hand**» 1) қул (рука); 2) хайвонларнинг олдинги оёқлари (лапа) 3) тараф (сторона положения), 4) бошқариш (контроль положения) 5) розилик, ваъда (согласия,обещание); 6) ёрдам (помощь) 7) бир уйинчи қулидаги карта (карты, исходящиеся на руках у одного игрока); 8) ишчи (рабочий); 9) денгизчи (матрос); 10) бажарувчи шахс (исполнитель, автор); 11)бир тудам одам (компания, группа); 12) уста (мастер); 13) эпчиллик (ловкость,); 14)ёзув, хат (почерк); 16) қарсақлар (аплодисменты); 17) манба (источник); 18) соат стрелкаси (стрелка); 19) қанот (крыло); 20) боғлам, даста (пучок); 21) қафт (ладонь) 22) сон гушти (окорок); 23) жилов (повод)

As can be seen from the above only some meanings may be described as identical but others are different. The correlated words «**hand**» and «**қўл**» may be the components of different phraseological units:

Besides that the correlated words in English and in Uzbek may coin different derivatives. For example. «**hand**» (handful, handless, handy, handily. handiness, hand v), «**қўл**» (қўл, қўлла, қўлсиз, қўлли). The verb «to taken» does not coincide in the number of meanings with its corresponding word «**олмоқ**».

For example, to take an exam — имтихон топширмак (с давать экзамен); to take tea – чой ичмок (пить чай); to take off — ечинмок (раздеваться); имтихон олмок (принимать экзамен) — to give an examination; дам олмок (отдыхать) — to have a rest; расм олмок(фотографировать)- to photograph. In the semantic structure of the Uzbek word there may be a definite figurative meaning which its corresponding English word doesn't possess. For example. Бу воқеа менга катта мактаб бўлди (Это событие было для меня уроком.) This event was a good lesson to me (not «this event was a good school to me»).

The norm of lexical valancy of a word in English is not the same as in Uzbek. For example. In Uzbek the verb « кутармоқ » (поднимать) may be combined with the nouns» кул » (ру ка) and «смул » (с тул). However, its corresponding English verb «to raise» can be combined with the noun «hand» («to raise hands but not «to raise chair» (to lift chair). [1,2,3,4,5]

The number of English synonymic sets may be substituted by one word in Uzbek. For example. The verbs «accept», «admit», «adopt», «take», «receive» correspond to the meanings of the Uzbek word « кабул қилмоқ »(принимать). In English to the Uzbek word « rassom » (художник) correspond three words. They are: painter, artist, drawer. In Uzbek 6 words are used to express the notion «blow» (уриш, зарба, зарб, урилиш, тақиллатиш, тешиш). In English more than 20 words denote this notion. They are: blow, smack, slap, whack, poke, dig, rap, knock, stroke etc. The correlated words «to make» and «қилмоқ;» have different lexical valancies. to make soup — шурва қилмоқ (пиширмоқ) (готовить суп), to make tea — чой дамламоқ (заварить чай), to make a table — стол ясамоқ (сделать стол,) дарс қилмоқ (готовить урок) — to do lessons, телефон қилмоқ (позвонить) — to ring up, ният қилмоқ (желать доброе) — to wish, ҳаракат қилмоқ (стараться) — to try etc.

Some languages are remarkably rich in words with specific meanings, while others utilize general terms and neglect unnecessary details. French is usually regarded as a highly abstract language, whereas German is fond of concrete, particular terms. German has three or four specific verbs corresponding to one generic term in French: French will often use a derivative where German and English have a more specific compound: cendrier — ashtray, aschenbecher; theiere — teapot...

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